

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP5. Learning Living Lab - Brussels
T5.3. Co-design and evaluation of alternative solutions

Deliverable 5.3b

REPORT ON THE CO-CREATION AND EVALUATION OUTCOMES

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Implementing a school street that would improve the safety of pupils was the aim of the second loop of the Brussels Looper Living Lab. Having learned from the first loop, the exchanges with parents and residents took place both during evening workshops as well as in front of the school gate when pupils were being picked up. This approach increased the input we received about the school street and traffic safety in general. Despite this new approach, the participation of parents and residents in the implementation of the school street was very low.

During exchanges with parents and residents, the Living Lab team found that the majority was favourable towards implementing a school street. This was also confirmed by a survey that was sent out: a minority of respondents selected 'improved accessibility by car' as a criterion to evaluate the impact of the school street on.

The Living Lab team had planned to modify and improve the school street by making changes during the implementation. However, two weeks after the school street had started, it was shut down due to the outbreak of COVID-19 in Belgium. This means that stage of the co-design and evaluation of solutions was not reached.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1.Objective of this deliverable

The second stage of the Looper co-creation approach is the co-design and evaluation of solutions. This deliverable discusses the findings and experiences of this stage in the second loop of the Brussels Living Lab, whose thematic focus is traffic safety.

1.2.Related deliverables

This deliverable on the Brussels Looper Living Lab is a continuation of the living lab implementation plan (deliverables 5.1a and 5.1b) and the report on the outcomes of the problem identification phase (deliverables 5.2a and 5.2b). The Looper Living Labs in Manchester and Verona have the same deliverables, respectively deliverables 7.1a and 7.1b, 7.2a and 7.2b, and 7.3a and 7.3b for Manchester and deliverables 6.1a and 6.1b, 6.2a and 6.2b, and 6.3a and 6.3b for Verona.

This deliverable draws on the following deliverables:

- Integrating evaluation tools in the Looper platform (deliverable 3.3)
- Guidelines for living labs (deliverable 4.1)
- Framework for monitoring and evaluation in Living Labs (deliverable 4.2)

2. PLANNING OF THE CO-DESIGN STAGE

2.1. Collect ideas through exchange sessions

The Looper team has decided to go to the people instead of waiting for the people to come to them. The team will therefore be present at the school for informal exchange sessions with parents, teachers and residents. These exchange sessions will be organized in the afternoon, at the school gate.

Before starting of the school street, these exchange sessions aim to inform the parents, teachers and residents about the possibility of a school street. After explaining the concept of a school street, the team will ask about the parents' fears or hopes regarding traffic safety. This feedback will be used to adapt the proposed plan.

The same sessions will also be organized during the school street test. The aim will be to evaluate the test with parents and residents along the way and modify some elements if necessary.

2.2. Co-design workshops

Next to these more individual exchanges, two information sessions will be organized: one in the afternoon and one in the evening. The municipality will be present to discuss with the participants about the school street and how to best organize the test.

A second workshop will be organized a few weeks before the end of the test, in order to evaluate the school street. The objective is to collect information about potential problems of the test and to find solutions. At the end of the workshop, the participants should decide if a new test is necessary or if the school street can be permanent. This will of course be shared with the municipality for an official green light.

2.3. Online

The Looper online platform will be used to collect and share ideas from citizens and stakeholders from a broader geographical area.

2.4. MCA and MAMCA analysis

A multi-criteria analysis (MCA) will be used to find out the impacts of the co-designed ideas on the sustainability of the Dailly neighbourhood. The multi-actor multi-criteria analysis (MAMCA) will show the expected stakeholder support for each co-designed idea. VUB-MOBI will interview the identified stakeholders in order to perform the MAMCA.

3. CO-DESIGN STAGE

3.1. Meeting people in the streets through exchange sessions

Five exchange sessions took place before the school street was implemented. At each exchange session, the Looper team would talk to about 10 to 20 parents, teachers or residents.

Parents were generally in favour of a school street. Some parents worried about the new location of the kiss & ride. Children that are brought to school by car would have to walk from the kiss & ride to the school on their own. As a response to this, the school organized a *pedibus*, i.e. older pupils would walk with the younger pupils from the kiss & ride at the end of the street to the school.

Residents were concerned about traffic transferring from the closed street to the adjacent ones. In order to verify if this was the case, traffic counts were organized before and during the test.

3.2. Workshops

The Looper team printed a large map of the neighbourhood in order to draw and design the different elements of the school street with the parents and residents, e.g. the location of the kiss & ride. The idea was also to broaden the discussion and talk about traffic safety and mobility of the neighbourhood in general.

Later in the project, an evaluation workshop would allow us to check the practical aspects of the school street as well as the impact on the neighbourhood.

3.2.1. Afternoon co-design workshop

Attendance: None

Content: The focus of this session was more on the parents and the pupils, as it was organized in the early afternoon. The aim was to look at elements such as the kiss & ride or the schedule and verify that these were adapted to the parents and pupils' needs.

Results: None

Communication: Flyering and face-to-face invitation during the exchange sessions

Experiences: Parents were all informed through the exchange sessions at the school gate. This showed that the communication was successful and that an extra co-design session was not really necessary.

3.2.2. Evening co-design workshop

Attendance: Very low

Content: This session focused on the mobility of the neighbourhood in general. The aim was to zoom out and point out potential problems that could emerge after implementing the school street. Together with the mobility experts from the municipality, participants would think about possible solutions to avoid them.

Results: One resident pointed out that this intervention would have a negative impact on the traffic in adjacent streets.

Communication: Flyering and face-to-face invitation during the exchange sessions

Experiences: It seems that information and co-design sessions for such a small intervention does not attract a broader public.

3.3.Online

No proposals were submitted on the online Looper platform because it had not yet been promoted.

4. EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABILITY IMPACTS

4.1. Sustainability MCA

The sustainability impacts of the co-designed alternatives were to be evaluated using multi-criteria analysis (MCA). The results of the sustainability MCA rank the alternatives on their sustainability scores and show which alternative is the most or least sustainable. Since the outcome of an MCA is influenced by external factors and uncertainties, the results of a sustainability MCA should be seen as a movement towards the best possible solution(s) rather than the best solution.

The weights and criteria used in the sustainability MCA come from the NISTO¹ project. The criteria are based on the three pillars of sustainability – economy, environment, social – and are based on case studies, a review of transport evaluation schemes, and the ranking of potential criteria by 214 stakeholders from the NISTO partner regions in a survey. The three pillars of sustainability were assigned equal weights, and the weights of the criteria within the pillars are based on the answers of 93 governmental representatives in North-West Europe.

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19 and the lockdown, the school street was cancelled, and no evaluation could take place.

¹ <https://www.nisto-project.eu>

5. EVALUATION OF STAKEHOLDER SUPPORT

5.1.MAMCA

Multi-actor multi-criteria analysis (MAMCA) is a methodology that assesses stakeholder preferences. MAMCA differs from MCA in that it explicitly introduces stakeholders before the criteria and weights are defined, which can increase the acceptance of the proposed solution by the different stakeholders. Whereas MCA has one set of criteria and weights, each stakeholder group in a MAMCA defines their own. The weights reflect the importance a stakeholder gives to each criterion.

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19 and the lockdown, the school street was cancelled, and no evaluation could take place. The text below describes the first steps that were taken in the evaluation using MAMCA.

5.1.1.Criteria residents

Residents from the neighbourhood were asked what aspects around the neighbourhood were important to them. In this part of the survey, respondents could select one or multiple criteria that they felt was important around the neighbourhood. Overall, it emerged that improved air quality was the most important criterion (19 votes), followed by more opportunities for social interaction (18 votes) and improved traffic safety and (15 votes). The total distribution of votes among the criteria can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Distribution of votes for criteria residents

The respondents were also asked to distribute a total of 100 points among the criteria that they had selected. Combining the inputs from respondents, we see that improving air quality, increasing opportunities for social interaction, and improving traffic safety are the most important criteria for residents (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Distribution of weights among criteria residents

5.1.2. Criteria parents

Parents were asked what aspects around the neighbourhood were important to them. In this part of the survey, respondents could select one or multiple criteria that they felt was important around the neighbourhood. Overall, it emerged that improved traffic safety, increased accessibility by foot or bicycle, and improved air quality were the most important aspects (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 Distribution of votes for criteria parents

The respondents were also asked to distribute a total of 100 points among the criteria that they had selected. Combining the inputs from respondents, we see that improving traffic safety, increasing accessibility by foot or bicycle, and improving air quality are the most important criteria for parents (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 Distribution of weights among criteria parents

6. IMPLEMENTATION OF CO-DESIGNED IDEA

The implementation of the school street was organised by the school principal, with help from the Looper team. It was difficult to attract residents or parents to the workshops, or even integrate them in the practical aspects of the school street, although the co-design plan listed a diversified channel of communication and methods, including:

- Distribution of flyers and organisation of information sessions for a first general communication.
- Co-design workshops for a wider overview of the mobility in the neighbourhood, in order to broaden the scope of the project.
- Face-to-face discussions for a personal approach.
- Surveys and an online platform for 24/7 participation options.

The engagement of the neighbourhood was very low. One explanation for the absence of participation could be the short period of the test and the fact that it has very low impact on the neighbourhood.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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